

The Influence of Empowerment Leadership on Intrinsic Motivation of Employees in The Environmental Services Binjai City Living

Rukun^{1*}, Abdi Sugiarto²

Magister Manajemen, Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: Tariganrukun94@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of empowerment leadership on intrinsic motivation in the Binjai City Environmental Service. This research was conducted using a causal associative quantitative approach. The sample used was all employees with a total of 75 people taken using proportional sampling. The research results show that empowering leadership has a positive and significant effect on intrinsic motivation. This is shown by the T-count value of T-count of 9.919 > t table 1.6666, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. The regression coefficient shows that if empowerment leadership is increased by 1 unit, then intrinsic motivation will increase by 0.364 units. assuming other variables remain constant. Apart from that, the results of the determination test show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.568 or 56.80%, which indicates that empowerment leadership has a low influence on intrinsic motivation, while the remaining 43.20% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. Thus, partially, empowering leadership has a positive and significant effect on the work of employees at the Binjai City Environmental Service. This identifies that meaning, improvements in empowering leadership can contribute to increased intrinsic motivation.

Keywords: empowerment leadership; intrinsic motivation

INTRODUCTION

Empowerment leadership is a leadership pattern that provides authority and support to subordinates to take initiative and responsibility in their tasks (Yurika & Rosita, 2022). A phenomenon that often occurs is the active participation of employees in the decision-making process, initiative in completing tasks, and open communication between superiors and subordinates.

The results of the 2020 Gallup Engagement Index survey show that organizations with high levels of active employee participation tend to have higher levels of productivity and lower turnover rates. This shows that when employees are given the opportunity to take initiative and responsibility in their duties, they tend to be more involved and contribute positively to the success of the organization (Gallup, 2020)

Organizations must have quality and innovation in improving performance and public services, one of which is improving their human resources (Yulk, 2020). In facing change and the era of digitalization, the role of a leader is very important, a leader will be required to continuously come up with creative ideas so that the business he runs can improve its performance in all fields and can survive or be able to adapt to environmental changes (Mulyadi, 2018)

Employee intrinsic motivation includes internal encouragement that encourages them to do their work with enthusiasm and dedication because of personal satisfaction or interest, not simply because of external rewards or pressure (Widyaputra & Dewi, 2017). Meanwhile, psychological empowerment refers to an individual's perception of the

availability of psychological resources such as autonomy, competence, and supportive relationships in the work environment (Santoso & Izzati, 2023).

Based on the results of initial observations by researchers at the Binjai City Environmental Service office, there were several problems that occurred. First, there is a lack of employee participation in the decision-making process. This shows that the views and experiences of other employees are not utilized optimally in making important decisions, which can hinder their performance and motivation.

Many factors can influence employee motivation at work. In this study, the researcher limited it to the empowerment leadership variable. Intrinsic motivation is a person's desire to do something without the need for external stimulation. Intrinsic motivation is motivated by positive thinking (Wahyuni et al., 2022).

Meanwhile, according to (Sadirman, 2014) intrinsic motivation is motives that become active or function without needing to be stimulated from outside, because within each individual there is already an urge to do something.

In this research, the definition of intrinsic motivation refers to the opinion of (Abdul Malik, 2019) which states that intrinsic motivation is a driver of enthusiasm that originates from within oneself who feels satisfied in carrying out the work to produce the integrity of organizational goals and individual goals where both can be satisfied through awareness of the importance of the benefits or meaning of work.

To measure intrinsic motivation in this research, it refers to the indicators established by Robbins in (Abdul Malik, 2019) which include:

- 1) Achievement is the opportunity given by the company to employees who excel;
- 2) Awards are giving awards to employees for their work to develop themselves;
- 3) Responsibility is the employee's duty to properly understand the role and authority carried out by the company;
- 4) Opportunities for advancement and development are opportunities for employees to develop and develop in terms of work.

Empowerment Leadership is "Super Leadership", which means individuals direct themselves. The terminology "Super Leadership" can also be called guided participation, where the leader helps his subordinates make their own decisions regarding their work (Amundsen & Martinsen, 2014).

Empowering leadership with its characteristics eliminates bureaucratic obstacles, helps subordinates find the meaning of work, gives subordinates the opportunity to make their own work decisions, can make subordinates feel involved and trusted in their abilities. This can increase subordinates' self-efficacy which helps them organize and carry out their work as well as possible (Ahluwalia & Puji, 2020a).

According to Amundsen & Martinsen (2014), indicators of empowering leadership include several elements that show a leader's efforts to empower subordinates or team members, namely:

- 1) Delegation of Responsibility.
- 2) Providing Support and Guidance.
- 3) Encourage Participation.

- 4) Providing Access to Resources and Information.
- 5) Providing Constructive Feedback.
- 6) Encouraging Innovation and Creativity.
- 7) Building Trust and Openness.
- 8) Providing Recognition and Appreciation.

The aim of this research is to investigate the influence of empowering leadership on the intrinsic motivation of employees at the Binjai City Environmental Service. It is hoped that the results of this research can provide a deeper understanding of the factors that influence employee intrinsic motivation at the Binjai City Environmental Service, as well as the potential implications. on organizational performance and effectiveness. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research with the aim of analyzing the pattern of relationships between variables with the aim of finding out the influence between two independent variables (exogenous) on the dependent variable (endogenous) (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). This research was carried out at the Binjai City Environmental Service. This research was carried out from March to May 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn. In this study, the population used was the entire number of employees in the Binjai City Environmental Service, totaling 75 people.

The sampling technique used in this research was a saturated sample. According to Sugiyono (2019) Saturated sampling is a sample selection technique if all members of the population are sampled, where the entire population in this study is sampled, namely 75 employees.

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Intrinsic motivation

X = Empowerment leadership

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). According to (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013) the determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely Empowerment Leadership (X), on the dependent variable, namely Intrinsic Motivation (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

a) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest score, the rating score and the standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Empowerment leadership	75	3.10	5.00	4.3720	.50015
Intrinsic motivation	75	3.30	5.00	4.2600	.47334
Valid N (listwise)	75				

From the table above, it shows that the measurement results show that respondents rated Empowerment Leadership and Intrinsic Motivation in the Binjai City Environmental Service as above average, with mean values of 4,372 and 4,260 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is high, with almost the same standard deviation (0.500 for Empowering leadership and 0.473 for Intrinsic motivation), indicating that although there are individual differences in perception, the majority of respondents have a fairly positive view of these two variables.

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 2. Validity Test Results for the Empowerment Leadership Variable (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
X1	0.860 > 0.2272	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X2	0.940 > 0.2272	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X3	0.900 > 0.2272	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X4	0.886 > 0.2272	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X5	0.851 > 0.2272	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X6	0.855 > 0.2272	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X7	0.862 > 0.2272	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X8	0.869 > 0.2272	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that the indicators for the empowerment leadership variable have a correlation coefficient of > 0.2272 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the indicators for the empowerment leadership variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2017).

Table 3. Validity Test Results of Intrinsic Motivation Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
Y.1	0.832 > 0.2272	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.2	0.866 > 0.2272	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.3	0.822 > 0.2272	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.4	0.822 > 0.2272	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that all indicators for the intrinsic motivation variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.2272 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the statements for the intrinsic motivation variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2016).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2016) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (a) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (a) value is > 0.61 .

Table 4. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Empowerment leadership	0.957	8
Intrinsic motivation	0.853	4

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (a) value of the Empowerment Leadership and Intrinsic Motivation variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

c) Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 5. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	4,254	1,292		3,293	,002
Empowerment leadership	,364	,037	,758	9,919	,000

Dependent Variable: Intrinsic motivation

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 4.254 + 0.364X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 4.254 means that if there is no empowering leadership, then there is intrinsic motivation of 4.254 points. The empowerment leadership regression coefficient is 1.594, meaning that empowerment leadership influences an increase in intrinsic motivation of 1.594 for every 1 point increase

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.758a	,574	,568	1.25745	,574	98,382	1	73	,000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Empowering leadership

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.568 or 56.80%, which means that empowering leadership has a moderate influence on intrinsic motivation, while the remaining 43.20% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of empowerment leadership on intrinsic motivation in the Binjai City Environmental Service

Ha: There is an influence of empowerment leadership on intrinsic motivation in the Binjai City Environmental Service

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 7. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	4,254	1,292		3,293	,002
Empowerment leadership	,364	,037	,758	9,919	,000

Dependent Variable: Intrinsic motivation

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is 9.919 > t table 1.6666, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted or there is a positive and significant influence between empowering leadership on intrinsic motivation in the Environmental Service. Binjai City.

Contents of Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of empowerment leadership on intrinsic motivation, this finding is in line with research results (Hanani, 2017) which show that empowerment leadership has a positive and significant effect on intrinsic motivation.

This concept highlights that when leaders are able to empower subordinates by providing responsibility, trust, and autonomy in their work, this not only improves individual performance but also strengthens their intrinsic motivation (Djaluputro & Andrias, 2023). Empowerment leadership refers to a leadership style that allows subordinates to take an active role in decision making and carrying out daily tasks. This promotes a sense of ownership of work, increases creativity, and reduces burnout levels. Thus, integration of these findings with your research context shows that implementing empowering leadership can be an effective strategy in optimizing intrinsic motivation in the work environment (Ahluwalia & Puji, 2020).

These findings have significant implications in the managerial context and organizational practice. The integration of empowering leadership which was found to

have a positive effect on employee intrinsic motivation shows the importance of developing a leadership style that provides room for autonomy, responsibility and support for individual initiative. Effective implementation of these practices can improve overall organizational performance by strengthening work quality, productivity, and employee retention, as well as creating a positive work culture that encourages collaboration and innovation. However, challenges such as slow cultural change and resistance to change need to be overcome with consistency in implementing this strategy at all levels of the organization to maximize its long-term benefits.

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of the research data analysis and discussion described above, it can be concluded that:

1. Hypothesis test results show that empowering leadership has a positive effect on intrinsic motivation. This can be seen from the T-count value of $9.919 > t$ table 1.6666, with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This regression coefficient shows that if empowerment leadership is increased by 1 unit, then the change in intrinsic motivation as seen from the Y value will increase by 0.364 units assuming other variables are considered constant. Thus, partially empowering leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the Binjai City Environmental Service.
2. Based on the results of the termination test, it shows that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.568 or 56.80%, which means that empowerment leadership has a low influence on intrinsic motivation, while the remaining 43.20% is influenced by other factors that have not been researched.

Suggestions

Based on the findings, discussion and conclusions from this research, several things can be suggested to the institution, namely the Binjai City Environmental Service Office, namely as follows:

1. Provide continuous training and development for leaders and managers in organizations. This training should focus on how to implement empowering leadership practices, such as giving more responsibility to subordinates, facilitating collective decisions, and creating a work environment that supports individual initiative.
2. Evaluate the impact and implementation of empowerment leadership regularly. This evaluation can be carried out through employee satisfaction surveys, analysis of individual and team performance, as well as monitoring employee retention and loyalty levels. By having robust data on the positive impact that empowering leadership produces, institutions can identify areas that need to be improved or refined in their leadership practices. In addition, the results of this evaluation can be used as a basis for developing further strategies to increase the effectiveness of empowerment leadership and strengthen intrinsic motivation and overall organizational performance.

REFERENCES

- Abdul Malik, FR (2019). The Influence of Intrinsic Motivation, Extrinsic Motivation and Work Experience on Employee Performance at PT. PLN (Persero) UP3 Medan [Muhammadiyah University of North Sumatra].<http://repository.umsu.ac.id/bitstream/handle/123456789/6558/SKRIPSI%20R.%20FAUZAN%20ABDUL%20MALIK.pdf?sequence=1>
- Ahluwalia, L., & Puji, K. (2020a). The Effect of Empowering Leadership on Performance and Homework Balance during the Covid-19 Pandemic.
- Ahluwalia, L., & Puji, K. (2020b). The Influence of Empowering Leadership on Homework Performance and Balance during the Covid-19 Pandemic.
- Amundsen, S., & Martinsen, L. (2014). Empowering Leadership: Construct Clarification, Conceptualization, and Validation of a New Scale. *Leadership Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.1016>
- Djaluputro, S., & Andrias, MS (2023). Analysis of Leadership Style in Employee Engagement at PT. DMI: Qualitative Case Study. *Ocean Journal of Economics and Business*, 14(3), 514–529.<https://doi.org/10.33059/jseb.v14i3.8230>
- Gallup. (2020). State of the Global Workplace 2022 Report. Gallup.
- Ghozali, I. (2016). *Multivariate Analysis Applications with the IBM SPSS 23 Program (Edition 8)*. Printing VII. Diponegoro University Publishing Agency.
- Hanani, N. (2017). *The Effect of Empowering Leadership on Intrinsic Motivation with Psychological Empowerment as a Mediator*. Gajah Mada University. <http://etd.repository.ugm.ac.id/>
- Kuncooro, Munajad. (2013). *Research Methods for Business and Economics*. Edition 4. Erlangga.
- Mulyadi. (2018). *Organizational Behavior and Service Leadership. (Concepts and Applications of Modern Administration, Management & Organization)*. Alfabet.
- Sadirman. (2014). *Teaching and Learning Interaction and Motivation*. Rajawali Press.
- Santoso, SDP, & Izzati, UA (2023). The Relationship between Psychological Empowerment and Innovative Behavior in Teachers in Vocational High Schools. . . *Character*, 10(02).
- Sugiyono. (2017). *Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods*. CV. Alfabet.
- Sugiyono. (2018). *Combination Research Methods (Mixed Methods)*. CV. Alfabet.
- Sugiyono. (2019). *Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methodologies and R&D*. Alfabet.
- Wahyuni, DT, Tadung, E., & Fadli, A. Muh. D. (2022). Intrinsic Motivation on Employee Performance in the Organization and Personnel Section of the Konawe Regency Regional Secretariat: Intrinsic Motivation on Employee Performance in the Organization and Personnel Section of the Konawe Regency Regional Secretariat. *Journal of Government Science (GovSci): Journal of Government Science*, 3(1), 63–73. <https://doi.org/10.54144/govsci.v3i1.26>
- Widyaputra, KA, & Dewi, AASK (2017). The Influence of Intrinsic Motivation on Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance at PT. Bussan Auto Finance. Udayana

University Management E-Journal, 7(1),
85.<https://doi.org/10.24843/EJMUNUD.2018.v7.i01.p04>

Come on. (2020). *Leadership in Organizations*. Pearson Education, Inc.

Yurika, E., & Rosita, S. (2022). The Influence of Servant Leadership on Innovative Behavior with Psychological Empowerment as an Intervening Variable at the Energy and Mineral Resources Service of Jambi Province. *Journal of Applied Management and Finance*, 11(03), 516–529.<https://doi.org/10.22437/jmk.v11i03.17974>